

susceptibility to aluminum toxicity. Two varieties (IR26 and IR36), 3 plant ages (10-, 20-, and 30-day-old seedlings), and 3 aluminum concentrations (0, 30, and 60 ppm) were used. At a specified plant age, seedlings were transferred to a plastic tray containing culture solution and different levels of aluminum. They were grown for 14 days in a glasshouse room maintained at 29°/21° C (day/night) with natural light and 70% relative humidity.

IR26 and IR36 showed a similar trend. A larger difference was found in shoot weight than in root weight (see table). Stunted growth in 10-day-old seedlings was noticed at 60 ppm Al.

Effect of seedling age and aluminum concentration on average root and shoot weights of 2 rice varieties grown in culture solution at IRR1.^a

Seedling age (days)	Al added (ppm)	Root weight		Shoot weight	
		mg/plant	% of check	mg/plant	% of check
10	0	83	100	266	100
	30	69	83	171	64
	60	62	74	132	49
20	0	298	100	908	100
	30	272	91	878	96
	60	238	79	830	91
30	0	677	100	2143	100
	30	544	80	2032	94
	60	499	73	2159	100

^aFigures are mean values of IR26 and IR36.

These results indicate that, in soils where aluminum toxicity is a potential problem, planting dapog (about 11 days

old) seedlings is not advisable. Twenty-day-old or even older seedlings would minimize risk of stand failure. ■

Comparison of zinc sulfate and Zn-EDTA as foliar spray

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Chelated formulations of zinc (particularly Zn-EDTA) have been recommended as foliar spray. The absorption efficiencies of Zn-EDTA and conventional ZnSO₄ + lime spray were compared in a pot experiment.

A silty clay loam soil containing 1.30 ppm DTPA extractable Zn was used at 2 kg/pot. Two 20-day-old Jaya seedlings in each of 20 pots were sprayed with one of 5 Zn treatments 15 days after transplanting. Treatments, replicated 4 times, were: control (no Zn); 100 ppm Zn as 0.044% ZnSO₄ + 0.022% lime spray; 100 ppm Zn as chelated Zn (manufacturer's recommended rate); 1,130 ppm Zn as 0.5 ZnSO₄ + 0.25% lime (recommended spray), and 1,130 ppm Zn as chelated zinc (Sukshmin-Z).

Both ZnSO₄ and chelated Zn foliar spray increased dry matter and Zn uptake over the control (Fig. 1). Yield with 100 ppm chelated Zn was 37% higher than the control. Dry matter yield and Zn uptake did not differ significantly with 100 ppm and 1,130 ppm Zn as ZnSO₄, nor with 100 ppm and 1,130 ppm chelated Zn.

1. Effect of zinc foliar sprays on rice dry matter yield and zinc uptake.

2. Effect of zinc foliar sprays on rice uptake of copper, iron, and manganese.

However, Zn uptake with 1,130 ppm chelated Zn was 33% higher than with 1,130 ppm ZnSO₄. Zn uptake with 100 ppm chelated Zn was 12% higher

than uptake with 100 ppm ZnSO₄, but the increase was not statistically significant.

Foliar sprays of ZnSO₄ and chelated

Zn increased copper uptake significantly but had no significant effect on either iron or magnesium uptake (Fig. 2). ■

Announcements

New rice publication

The Tropical Products Institute of London announces publication of *Bibliography of rice parboiling 1950-1980* by Ruth Kasasian. The 55-page report is a comprehensive annotated list of scientific publications on such topics as par-

boiling technique, drying, milling, infestation resistance, cooking and canning, composition, nutritional aspects, bran and oil, consumer reaction, economics of parboiling, and testing. It includes an author index and a technical index.

Price is £2.00, including packing and postage. Governmental and educational

establishments, research institutions, and nonprofit organizations working in countries eligible for British aid may receive single copies without charge.

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